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ROLE OF STRESS ON EMPLOYEE TURNOVER

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ABSTRACT

Stress is a dynamic condition in which an opportunity, constraint or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcomes is perceived to be both uncertain and important. Stress is a complex phenomenon. It is very subjective experience. Stress is common phenomenon of human life which occurs due to dissatisfaction everyone has to face on daily basis nobody can avoid it and it affect to work life as well as personal life. Employee turnover is also affected by the stress because dissatisfaction level of employees, no one can survive with stressful environment that employee turnover is high when there is high satisfaction level and vice versa. This study has found the effect of stress on employee's turnover for this we have tried to search out impact of stress on employee turnover and also the relationship between the stress and employee turnover. We have used regression, co relation and reliability statistical tools to study these objectives.

Key words: *Stress, employee turnover, phenomenon*

Introduction

Stress is a dynamic condition in which an opportunity, constraint or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcomes is perceived to be both uncertain and important. Stress is a complex phenomenon. It is very subjective experience. What may be challenge for one will be a stressor for another? It depends largely on background experiences, temperament and environmental conditions. A certain level of stress is unavoidable. Because of its complex nature stress has been studied for many years by researchers in psychology, sociology and medicine. Stress is a general term applied to various mental and physiological pressures experienced by people feel in their lives. Stress is a part of life and is generated by constantly changing situations that a person must face. The term stress refers to an internal state, which results from frustrating or unsatisfying conditions.

Employee turnover

Turnover can be caused by employees who leave on their own. This is called voluntary turnover. When an employee leaves because of a layoff or a disciplinary firing this is called involuntary turnover. The total of the two is called total turnover.

Employee Turnover is the Percentage of a company's employees who leave during a specified period. Although it is most often expressed at annual turnover rate, the calculation can be done for shorter or longer periods.

Review of literature

W.hom .peter and J. kinicki angelo (1991), This study generalized a leading portrayal of how job dissatisfaction progresses into turnover ([Horn & Griffeth, 1991](#)) and more rigorously tested this model using structural equations modeling and survival analysis, We further integrated job avoidance, interrole conflict, and employment conditions into this framework. Using a national survey of retail store personnel, we found that interrole conflict and job avoidance influence turnover indirectly, as the Hom-Griffeth model specifies, and that unemployment rates directly affect turnover.

Guimaraes Tor , Igbaria Magid (1999) As telecommuting programs proliferate, a better understanding of the relationship between telecommuting and career success outcomes is required to provide human resources managers, telecommuters, and information systems managers with information to decide the future of telecommuting arrangements. This paper addresses this need by exploring whether turnover intentions and their determinants differ for telecommuters and non-telecommuters. Four hundred salespeople from one large company in the southeastern United States were asked to participate in the study. The organization entry point was the marketing director. One hundred and four telecommuting employees and one hundred and twenty-one regular employees responded, with a total of 225 usable questionnaires. Telecommuters seemed to face less role conflict and role ambiguity and tended to be happier with their supervisors and more committed to their organizations. They also showed lower satisfaction with peers and with promotion. Based on the results, recommendations are proposed for managing the implementation of telecommuting programs and their impact on the rest of the organization's employee population.

G. Anderson james and toft gray pamelaa (1981), This study investigated the causes and effects of nursing stress in the hospital environment. It was hypothesized that the sources and frequency of stress experienced by nursing staff were functions of the type of unit on which they worked, levels of training, trait anxiety, and sociodemographic characteristics. It was also hypothesized that high levels of stress would result in decreased job satisfaction and increased turnover among the nursing staff. Data were collected from 122 nurses on 5 patient care units of a private, general hospital using a Nursing Stress Scale developed for this study, the IPAT Anxiety Scale, the Job Description Index, and personnel records. Analysis of variance, profile analysis, and path analysis were used to analyze these data. Three major sources of stress were identified: work load, feeling inadequately prepared to meet the emotional demands of patients and their families, and death and dying. The nature of these sources as well as their pervasiveness suggests that factors inherent in the nursing role particularly that of the registered nurse, are important determinants of stress. Differences in the frequency of stress among the units investigated suggest 2 additional factors that need to be examined in future studies: structural characteristics of units that affect the amount of role conflict and ambiguity staff experience, and personality characteristics that may attract nurses to specific units. As hypothesized, stress was found to have significant effects on job satisfaction and turnover.

Gupta Nina , Beehr Terry A. 1979 The relationship between four job stresses (role ambiguity, role overload, underutilization of skills, and resource inadequacy) and two employee withdrawal behaviors (absenteeism and turnover) was investigated. The joint prediction of employee withdrawal from measures of job stress and selected background variables was also investigated. Data were obtained regarding 651 employees in five organizations through personal interviews and company records. Analysis indicated that job stress is related to employee withdrawal behaviors, that prediction of subsequent behaviors is stronger than prediction of prior behaviors, and that the predictive power of job stress and background variables taken together is as strong as, or stronger than, the predictive

power of background variables alone. Confidence in the strength of the findings is enhanced by the use of multiple data sources and multiple data points.

Hatton, Chris; Emerson, Eric 1993, Collected questionnaire data from 64 direct-care staff members (aged 19–51 yrs) in a residential facility for people with multiple disabilities. Path analyses identified a number of organizational factors that predicted levels of perceived stress, overall job satisfaction, overall life satisfaction, and perceived likelihood of leaving the organization. Factors found to be common influences on all outcome measures included support from other staff (largely supervisory), job variety, staff perceptions of organizational democracy, goodness-of-fit between the attitudes and aims of staff and those of the organization, staff development, and income. (PsycINFO Database Record (c) 2012 APA, all rights reserved.

Objectives

The main objective of my study is to ensure the quality of company's process. Along with i consider the following point as an object during my study:

- 1) To check the reliability of the questionnaire.
- 2) To study effect of stress on employee turnover.
- 3) To study the relationship between the stress and employee turnover.

Research Methodology

"Research methodology is a process of planning, acquiring, analyzing and disseminating relevant data and information".

Null hypothesis

- There is no significant impact of Stress on employee turnover.
- There is no significant relationship between stress and employee turnover.

The study was based on descriptive in nature. We have used Convenient Sampling at JK tyre ltd. by individual respondents. The sample size was 70 and questionnaire method was used to collect the data and regression, co relation and reliability have been used to analyze and interpret the data.

Data Analysis

Reliability

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.599	11

In this project report reliability value is .599 of independent variable (stress). Which is considered as average and it can be seen that in almost all the reliability methods applied here, reliability value is average in all items on the questionnaire and all items are reliable.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.789	11

Model Summary ^b											
Model		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
						R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
dimension0	1	.279 ^a	.078	.064	6.57647	.078	5.743	1	68	.019	2.099
a. Predictors: (Constant), stress											
b. Dependent Variable: employeeturnover											
The value of adjusted R square is 0.064 that indicates independent variable stress explains 6.9% variance in dependent variable employee's turnover.											

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	248.378	1	248.378	5.743	.019 ^a
	Residual	2940.994	68	43.250		
	Total	3189.371	69			
a. Predictors: (Constant), stress						
b. Dependent Variable: employeeturnover						

In this project report reliability value is .789 of dependent variable (employees turnover). Which is considered as good and it can be seen that in almost all the reliability methods applied here, reliability value is good in all items on the questionnaire and all items are reliable.

Regression Analysis

The model used for regression has good fit as indicated by F-value 5.743 which is significant at 0.019 of level of significance indicating a substantial predictability of model.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	49.377	4.706		10.491	.000
	stress	-.335	.140	-.279	-2.396	.019

a. Dependent Variable: employeeturnover

Y = a +bx
 $Y = 49.377 + (-.335) x + \epsilon$
 Y = Employees Turnover (dependent variable)
 X = Stress
 ϵ = error

The relationship between stress as independent variable and employee's turnover as dependent variable is indicated by standardized coefficient Beta with a value of -2.79. The significance of beta is tested using T-test and value for model is -2.396 which is significant at 0.019 of level of significance indicating significant relationship between the variables.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis H₀: there is no significant impact of Stress on employee turnover.

The result indicates that there is significant impact of stress on employee's turnover (p = 0.19 > 0.05). Therefore null hypothesis is not accepted.

Correlation

To determine the strength of linear relationship between variable correlation, coefficient are calculated these correlation analysis were interpreted on the scal offered by gurilford (1956)

- (i) R<0.20 indicates slight, almost negligible relationship.
- (ii) R=0.20 to 0.40 indicates low correlation definite but small relationship.
- (iii) R=0.40 – 0.70 indicates moderate correlation substantial relationship. R= .70 – 0.90 shows high correlation.
- (iv) If are 0.90 is indicative of very high correlation very dependable relationship.

Correlations^a

		employeeturnover	stress
Employeeeturnover	Pearson Correlation	1	-.279*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.019
Stress	Pearson Correlation	-.279*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

a. Listwise N=70

The relationship between stress and employee's turnover is having substantial relationship as the value **r = -2.79** which according to Guilford (1956) the variables have substantial relationship.

Findings

Findings on the basis of the researcher observations

There was direct relationship between the stress and employee's turnover. Organization was not provided facility for self improvement of their employees and equal treatment in all matters like employee compensation and job security etc. Employees generally do regular work overtime that they felt unsafe at work place especially in case of women.

Suggestions

Company should understand that stress is major cause for their productivity so that it should be reduce at workplace and should maintained healthy working environment, regular development in infrastructure for betterment of the firm, treat equally in all matters like employee compensation and job security etc. and maintained training and development program me timely.

Conclusion

The research concluded with lot learning on our part. In this report we have analyzed **“Impact of Stress on Employee's Turnover”** The objective of the study was to identify the impact of stress on employee's turnover through primary data. To analyze the objective we have use different research methodology (test) such as reliability to check the reliability of the questions, the reliability of stress (independent variable) was .599, which was average and reliability of employee's turnover (dependent variable) was .789, which was good finally the regression analysis to find out the impact of stress on employee's turnover of the firm and null hypothesis was not accepted which was “there is no significant impact of stress on

employee's turnover" that means there was the significant impact of stress on employee's turnover hence there is relationship between the variables.

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